

Lines (no.) and their reactions to bacterial leaf streak during 1973 and 1975 kharif, Pantnagar, India.

Reaction	Lines (no.) from		
	AICRIP		IRRI ^a
	1973	1975	
Resistant	5	32	38
Moderately resistant	10	22	22
Moderately susceptible	22	64	21
Susceptible	25	933	252
Highly susceptible	23	230	7
Total	85	1281	340

^aInternational Rice Observational Nursery.

RP 975-145-3-3, RP 572-9-2-1, RP 572-9-5-1, RP 633-367-1-2, RP 633-385-2-7, RP 2001-25-1, RP 2003-1-2-5, RP 2004-1-6-3, RP 2007- CRHP-1, R 32-2617, R 27-2546, RJR 107-305, 2-25 (upland paddy x BR 4-10), 24-7-3 (SR 3-9 x TN1), R 7-2-3-1, R 7-3-1-1, R 8-12-1-1, R 19-1-1-1, R 106-2-1-3-2, IR2071-557-6-4, IR2071-588-1-1-1, IR2071-875-2-3-4, IR2071-636-5-2-6, BR 3-12-B-15-40, BR 51-67-1/CI, BR 51-74-2, BR 44-11-1, BR 51-99-1, BR 51-243-1, BR 51-319-9, BR 52-8-1, B 459b-Pu-4-5-6-5, IR2031-238-4-2-2-3, IR2035-290-2-3-1, Purple check (15/IR1103-1), IR2070-210-3-3-4, IR2588-19-1-1, IR2681-34-5-6, IR2871-53-2, IR3264-13-158-2-935-3, IR3265-138-2-5, BG 11-11, Chianung-Seu Yu 8, SRR 6726-76-2-3, BIC-Md-3-3, IR2031-724-2-3-4, IR2071-636-5-5, IR2070-423-2-5-6, IR2035-290-2-1-3, IR2848-26-1, IR944-102-2-3-2, TN1, IR1539-823-1-4, IR26, IR5492-3-147 (Glb₂), IR1820-52-24-1, IR2070-24-1-4-5, and JPS.

Moderately resistant — CR 139-1058, RP 633-590-3-1-1-1, RP 632-94-1-2-1-1, RP 744-104-76-1, RP 744-104-76, UPR 4 D-25-2,45457 (TN1/Co 29) x Hansa, HPNS 32, TR 14, RP 633-308-1-2, RP 938-31-4-6, RP 2001-9-1, R 102-2609, R 106-2567, R 111-2583, R 32-2615, R 22-2522, 12-2 (TN1/BR4-10), 11-2 (TN1/BR 4-10), BR 1-2B-40-3, BR 43-1-1-2, BR 51-46-5, BR 51-49-6, 31-14 (upland paddy x BR 4-10), R 1-1-1-1, IR2070-414-3-9, BR 51-114-2, BR 51-331-4, Giza 172, B 1896-52-8-3-1,

B441b-126-2-3-1, IR1544-181-1-1, IR2035-255-2-3-1, IR2063-65-2-1, IR2063-152-3-2, IR2063-185-2-2, IR2070-834-1-2, IR2153-550-2-6, IR2786-120-1, IR2843-26-3, IR2071-625-1-252, IR2070-743-6-3-2, SPR 6726-134-2-26, IR1545-339-2-2, and RP 633-200-1-7-4-1.

Methods to artificially inoculate and screen rice varieties for resistance to stem rot disease under field conditions

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Two methods of inoculation for stem rot were tested during 1975–76: 1) placing a mycelial mass on potato-dextrose-agar among the injured culms of the hills, and 2) placing inoculum from autoclaved rice grains in the hills and tying the hills as in the International Rice Sheath Blight Nursery (IRSHBN). Ten hills each of 104 varieties were inoculated; at grain maturity, the inoculated hills were cut at the base for evaluation. The rotten tillers were counted by pressing between the fingers. Thirty-two varieties and lines showed less than 30% culm rotting and were rated as resistant. The rices that showed less than 20% culm infection included IR32, IR1529-680-3-2, IR2053-87-3-1, IR2061-214-3-3-28, IR2061-214-3-3-32,

Two methods of artificial inoculation for stem rot disease. Bangladesh Rice Research Institute.

Cultivar	Rotten tillers (%)		
	Mycelial mass	Grain inoculum	Av.
Chitraj	15	25	20
IR1817-2-143-3	20	25	23
IR944-85-1-2-1-1	21	23	22
IR910-12-3-1-1	9	36	23
BR9-17-6-4	12	29	21
BR13-231-1	25	31	28
IR579-80-1-2-1	27	31	29
IR20	25	38	32
IR781-177-3-2-2	28	39	34
Mukti	27	43	35
Kataktara	31	43	37
BR9-17-4-2	19	54	37
IR836-1-1-1	29	49	39
BR43-11-2	35	45	40
IR8	25	81	53
Chandina H/R 29-3	36	75	56

and Mahsuri (Improved). The IRSHBN method of placing grain inoculum was more effective than the other as shown by the higher percentage of infection in 16 varieties (see table).

Sources of resistance to ufra disease of rice in Bangladesh

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Eight species of wild rice and one cultivar were screened for resistance to ufra disease in the field and in pots. The wild rice species were *Oryza glaberrima*, *O. nivara*, *O. officinalis*, *O. perennis*, *O. rufipogon*, *O. sativa* var. *patua*, *O. spontanea*, and *O. subulata*. The *O. sativa* cultivar was R16-06. All plants were inoculated at the vegetative stage by introducing into the leaf sheath cavities about 1 ml of nematode suspension (approx. 1,000 *D. angustus*/ml) with a fine glass dropper. The inoculated potted plants were covered with polyethylene bags for 2 days to maintain proper humidity.

All the rices, except the wild species *O. subulata* and the cultivar R16-06, showed symptoms of ufra infection. *O. subulata* could not be infected at all. Although infection began on inoculated R16-06, the disease did not fully develop and no nematodes could be isolated from the plants at the mature stage. R16-06 is a deep-water rice that is sensitive to photoperiod, but its yield potential is low. *O. subulata* is a stiff-leaved rice. These two rices can be used as sources of resistance in future breeding programs for deep-water rice.

Rice disease survey: 1975

Summarized by H. E. Kauffman, joint coordinator and plant pathologist; T. Ebron, senior research assistant; and S. Merca, research assistant, International Rice Testing Program, IRRI

Scientists responded well to disease survey questionnaires sent out with the Rice Pathology Newsletter in late 1975. As in previous years, blast was the most widespread disease during 1975. It was

the major disease in India, Iran, Senegal, Colombia, Mexico, USA, and France. Second in importance was bacterial blight, which was significant in most Asian countries. It was serious in Korea, Taiwan, and Bangladesh. There were no large outbreaks of tungro virus during 1975, but grassy stunt virus was closely associated with brown planthopper outbreaks and caused heavy losses in numerous areas of Java, Indonesia. Brown spot and narrow brown leaf spot, although widespread, generally caused minor losses.

Some scientists gave estimates of yield and monetary losses. Korea and Taiwan have organized surveys that provide reliable estimates. Other estimates are rough but they give a general idea of the serious losses caused by rice diseases. Blast, for example, was estimated to cause losses of more than US\$8 million in each of three countries: Taiwan, Iran, and Mexico. Sheath blight also caused about the same loss in South Korea and Taiwan. Bacterial blight was estimated to cause an average loss of 4% in Bangladesh, which amounted to about US\$96 million

In Indonesia, grassy stunt virus caused more than US\$20 million in crop losses. Even more important than the monetary

figure is the amount of rice that was lost in countries where food is already scarce. **W**

Respondents to the RPN rice disease survey: 1975.

Region, country	Respondent	Region, country	Respondent
East Asia		West Asia	
South Korea	B. K. Chung	Iran	M. Akhavizadegan M. Moafizad Plant Pest and Disease Institute
Taiwan	R. J. Chiu W. H. Tsai	Saudi Arabia	W. L. Chang
Southeast Asia		Sub-Sahara Africa	
Indonesia	A. Hasanuddin J. Soepriaman Sunendar L. T. Palmer	Ivory Coast	J. M. Bidaux
Philippines	D. Lapis B. S. Nunag, Jr. IRRI scientists	Nigeria	Y. A. Awoderu
Thailand	P. Weerapat	Senegal	J. C. Guard
South Asia		Europe	
Bangladesh	S. A. Miah	France	R. A. Marie
India	S. Kannaiyan G. Venkata Rao N. Shivanandappa B. M. Singh R. A. Shih Survey teams from Tamil Nadu Karnataka Punjab	South and Central America	
Sri Lanka	H. Weeraratne	Colombia	M. J. Rosero
		Mexico	L. H. Aragon J. L. Armenta Soto F. M. Cabrera
		North America	
		(Louisiana)	M. C. Rush
		Oceania	
		Australia	W. Pont
		Papua New Guinea	J. T. Hale

Major rice diseases in the world's rice-growing countries in 1975 (from RPN disease survey).